

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF TRANSLATION OF REALIA

Umarxonova Guliruxsor Murotxon qizi

Termez University of Economics and Service
Department of Foreign Language and Literature
2nd-year Master Student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14862700>

Abstract: This article discusses the unique features of translating realias and their significance in linguistics. Additionally, it presents reflections on the importance of realias in the translation process and explores different methods for translating realias.

Key words: Realia, translation studies, semantics, transliteration, additional explanations.

Translation serves the interests of expanding economic, political, scientific, and cultural relations between nations. It is regarded as one of the most essential forms of intercultural communication.

Essentially, translation means accurately and fully expressing previously conveyed information in one language using another language [1].

S.G. Ter-Minasova notes that “...the contradictions in mentalities become even more apparent when translated into a foreign language. This is because every language reflects the culture and mentality of its speakers. Information that sounds natural in the native language may take on an entirely different form in a foreign language” [2].

The emergence of a word as a realia is primarily linked to the region, country, nation, or ethnic group that created it. However, realias can gain significance in a particular culture and spread beyond national borders, sometimes even globally. According to the renowned translation studies scholar V.M. Rossels, “realia are words that enter the target language from the source language and refer to specific national, local objects, or concepts” [3].

Realias play a crucial role in translation studies, comparative linguistics, cultural studies, and ethnolinguistics by helping researchers examine linguistic and cultural differences. They also reflect the level of cultural interaction and encapsulate concepts related to a nation’s way of life. Realia are notions shaped throughout human civilization and correspond to historical periods when cultural distinctions became more pronounced. The key feature that distinguishes realia from other related concepts is their material significance—realia always refer to concrete objects. The original meaning of “realia” pertains

to objects that represent the unique characteristics of a culture. The etymology of the word “realia” itself is rooted in the Latin term meaning “material”.

During translation, the methods of rendering realia focus on reconstructing lexical semantics in another language. Various techniques are used for this purpose, one of which is transliteration. Transliteration helps maintain the national and cultural essence of the original word. For example: хужра – hujra, гузар– guzar, куроқ– kurok, тиллақош – tillakosh

However, transliteration is not always sufficient to convey the full meaning of realia. To reflect the pragmatic meaning of realia from the source language, additional explanations are often necessary. For instance:

“**Katlama (flat cakes)** are popular in many regions of Uzbekistan, but only Andijan bakers are capable of making them so large and fluffy.”

Realia add a unique cultural and emotional depth to literary texts. Their translation requires not only linguistic knowledge but also an understanding of cultural aspects.

Based on the above points, it can be concluded that an effective translation of Uzbek realia into English requires a combination of transliteration, translation, and explanatory methods. If these techniques are used appropriately, the artistic style of the translated text will be accurately conveyed.

References:

1. Fedorov A.V. Fundamentals of the General Theory of Translation. 4th edition. Moscow: Vyssh. shk., 1983, p. 36.
2. Ter-Minasova S.G. Language and Intercultural Communication. Moscow: Slovo/Slovo, 2004, p. 265.
3. Rossels V.M. Relay of Words: The Art of Literary Translation. Moscow: Znanie, 1972, p. 32.
4. Vlakhov S., Florin S. Untranslatable in Translation. Third edition, corrected. Moscow: Valent, 2006.

